

THE CONCEPT AND FORMATION OF HANDWRITING: WHAT HANDWRITING ANALYSIS ENTAILS AND HOW IT IS DEVELOPED

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Annotation

Since the dawn of civilization, handwriting has been one of the most important forms of communication. However, since handwriting varies from person to person, author identification has become a promising application of pattern recognition to determine the actual author of a handwritten document. The article discusses the signs and methods studied and applied in domestic forensic handwriting analysis. An overview of sources on forensic handwriting analysis is given for mentioning and describing general and specific signs in writing, its study and the possibility of using it in individual methods of forensic handwriting examination.

Key words: handwriting, twisting, masking, imitation, identification

Handwriting is a complex process. It takes an average person many years to learn to write in a way that others can decipher their words. Developing the coordination of hand, wrist, and finger movements necessary for writing text requires time. If we consider a person learning a second language, they will begin writing in that language after just a few lessons. Essentially, a person applies the motor and coordination skills they know from their native language and uses them artistically to produce the second language in written form. Writing skills acquired over a short period will continue to develop and evolve as the writer further hones their abilities. Writing skills develop in a person over a long time, and as such, they typically have a strong influence on an individual's handwriting. It is difficult to quickly alter movements to create letters in different styles. It is for these reasons that the handwriting of a mature person is identifiable.

Handwriting is a form of forensic science that is somewhat unique. With fingerprints or DNA, there is absolute identification. Handwriting, however, is somewhat subjective. It varies even for the same writer or within the same written document. Let's consider our own signature. If you write it on a sheet of paper several times, none of them will exactly replicate another. It is precisely through subjective observations of documents that it is determined whether two pieces of writing were executed by the same person. We know the number of people in the world. Now imagine that you can exclude all of them, except for one, based on a fragment of writing. It's difficult, but it's possible. The act of writing requires a complex set of skills that we start learning in elementary school. As children, we are shown pictures of letters and asked to imitate them by drawing corresponding letters. The letters are often on the blackboard, and we have models of lowercase and uppercase printed and cursive letters. These are standard forms that we are taught to imitate. It is only many years after we have mastered the skill of writing that we begin to deviate from the standard form and develop individual characteristics. Nevertheless, it is quite predictable that it is practically impossible

to determine the handwriting of a person who is immature or who has not developed sufficient individual characteristics that deviate from the textbook design taught in school.

One of the fundamental premises of handwriting analysis is that no two people write in exactly the same way. This assumption is based on unproven statistics. It is impossible to examine the handwriting of every living person and everyone who has ever lived to determine if anyone has extended handwriting that is completely identical. Short fragments of writing may appear similar, but extended samples of handwriting will always show sufficient deviation from the textbook design to allow for individualization. The same argument applies to fingerprints, as it is impossible to examine the fingerprints of all living and deceased individuals, but statistics indicate that it is impossible for two people (including twins) to have matching fingerprints. This is based on our motor skills. As with any forensic science, handwriting analysis can be divided into two categories.

The first is class characteristics, which are features found in the handwriting of groups of people.

The second is individual characteristics, which are traits unique to a single writer. Individual features can be observed in deviations from the standard or taught handwriting that we all learned. These deviations can be identified when they occur in sufficient quantity and uniqueness. Examples include slant, loops, terminal strokes, flourishes, etc. The handwriting of all people combines both class and individual characteristics. If there are enough individual characteristics, they can be identified. It is precisely through a sufficient number of handwriting samples from documents that one can determine the range of variations specific to a particular writer. In other words, in how many ways does a person form the letter "A" or how low do they cross the letter "p"? These characteristics can be mapped if a sufficient number of samples are written. Generally, the more experienced the writer, the more developed their individual characteristics become. Differences are inconsistent aspects of writing in two documents that make it impossible for two works to have been produced by the same person. Not all people have the same natural abilities. Some have more dexterity than others, which gives them more freedom in writing. Some have better hand, wrist, or finger coordination than others. Skills are acquired and cannot exceed natural aptitude. Skills can be quantitatively assessed by examining a person's ability to control size, slant, spacing, and writing speed.

The handwriting is also influenced by the writer's physical condition. Age, illness, drugs, alcohol or stroke - all of this can affect the quality of a person's writing. Conditions affecting handwriting can be temporary (drugs or alcohol), static (paralysis), or progressive (changeable disease). Typical symptoms of a mental illness, drug use, or intoxication that affect writing are distorted spaces, relative stroke size, and the structure of the letters. Physical problems typically manifest as trembling, writing device slipping, and letter shape changes. Nervousness and tension can also affect handwriting. The position of the writer can influence the writing, that is, bending, sitting, standing, in a limited space. The surface for writing can affect the quality of the writing, for example, a rough surface can create something that looks like a vibration in the writing. Finally, the writing apparatus can influence the appearance of the writing. Habit is an important factor in handwriting. After a person learns to write, it is his habits that contribute to the strengthening of his skills. Habit is what drives us from spelling to individualization. The location of the letter is another important feature. How is handwritten text placed on the document? The most important

factors are the use of fields, the alignment of signatures in the text, and the closeness of the writing.

When questioning whether a specific person has written a text or signature, the first step for the investigator is to obtain known samples or specimens of that person's handwriting. Some of the best samples are those obtained without the person's prior knowledge. In other words, if an investigator can acquire handwriting from undisputed business documents, the likelihood of intentional alteration is minimized. This effectively ensures "normal" writing. These types of known samples can be found in checkbooks, diaries, ledgers, handwritten letters, phone books, and even grocery lists. Additionally, the samples should be in the same style, such as cursive or block letters. Since handwriting changes throughout our lives, it's important to try to obtain comparative samples from approximately the same time period as the writing in question. When creating samples for comparative analysis, the person should use the same paper and writing implements as those used for the material under investigation. The investigator should also ensure that the samples were produced without using an awkward hand. Right-handed individuals should write with their right hand, and so on. If the document under investigation is on a form, the provided samples should be similar, as should the writing instrument used to create the text. The subject should not be shown the text in question. This is because if a person wrote the document with deliberate distortions, seeing it would remind them of what to do. After a sample is completed, it should be removed, and a new clean sheet of paper should be provided to repeat the process. By doing this multiple times, a natural range of variations can be obtained.

The Process The first step is to evaluate whether the handwriting is "normal." An example of abnormal handwriting would be text that constantly changes in slope, size ratio, and style. What to pay attention to during the examination: Normal handwriting: After determining the handwriting as normal, you can continue the examination. Otherwise, you'll need to stop and reassess. You must have a clear understanding of the features and variations. **Characteristics:** When conducting the examination, first analyze the general handwriting characteristics. What is the main movement used to create each stroke? Is the writer's main movement angular or more rounded, etc.? **Letter Formation:** To write the lowercase letter "a" does the writer begin with a long initial stroke, and is the letter angular or round, etc.? Where do the letters begin and how is each one formed? Are the letters written clockwise or counterclockwise? Are some letters connected while others are not? **Line quality:** Can the writer control their handwriting? Are there many pen lifts, or is the handwriting continuous and strong? Is the writing fluent, with smooth or clumsy letters? **Pressure:** Evaluate the writer's pressure. Is it excessive? Is there more pressure on downstrokes or upstrokes? **Shading:** Is there shading on certain letters, and is it consistent? **Slant:** In which direction is the slant? Are the strokes made from right to left or left to right? Is there no slant at all? Are the slant characteristics consistent? **Proportions:** Look at the letters and how they are proportional to each other. Every time the lowercase "v" is next to "b," is the "v" higher or lower? **Initial strokes:** Does the writer begin with an exaggerated initial stroke or with a short beginning? **Baseline:** Where is the text in relation to the baseline? Is the writing physically above, on, or below it? Is it slanted relative to the baseline? **Note:** The "baseline" can be imaginary.

Word frequency: Does the author use abbreviations in the writing? **Special signs or marks:** What is the length of the exclamation point or comma? Are the dots small points, quick

dashes forming a horizontal line, or are they missing? Speed: Is the writing produced smoothly? Are there numerous pauses? If so, are they always in the same place? Spacing: Consider the distance between words, letter combinations, and margins. After completing the sample analysis, you should have a clear understanding of the class and individual characteristics found in the person's writing. The range of variations and the consistency of individual characteristics should also be clear. Many experts keep working notes to track the numerous handwriting features they observe. This can be done by making a photocopy of the writing and using a highlighter to mark the characteristics. Relying on memory is problematic and can lead to errors and questioning in court. Relying on memory is problematic and leads to mistakes and interrogations in court.

Written under the question. The first step in studying the manuscript under investigation is to determine whether the entire text was written by one person. It's not an easy step. If there are signs that the main part of the letter uses different handwriting, styles, slopes, etc., then the parts that are not necessary for verification should be excluded from consideration.

The next step is to determine whether the handwriting is normal. To make this determination, it is necessary to perform at least three steps.

Distortion - These are changes in the text that may not be due to the fault or actions of the author.

Disguise - This is a deliberate attempt to conceal or alter the appearance of handwriting.

Imitation - This is an attempt to recreate someone else's handwriting based on a sample or from memory.

Identification (a definitive conclusion about identity): This is the highest degree of certainty expressed by document experts when comparing handwriting. There is no doubt, as the evidence contained in the samples and the document under investigation is the handwriting of the same person. Probability: The evidence is very convincing; however, some critical features or qualities are missing, and therefore identification is not justified (does not reach a practically certain degree of confidence). Nevertheless, there are virtually no doubts, and the signs quite convincingly indicate that the samples and the writings under investigation were written by the same person.

No conclusion (completely inconclusive, indeterminable): This is the zero point on the scale of certainty. It is used when there are substantially limiting factors, such as strong disguise in the material being studied and/or comparable material, or the absence of comparable writings, and it is impossible to lean towards any conclusion.

Probably not: The evidence quite convincingly indicates that the samples and the examined writings were not written by the same person. However, as in the probable range above, the evidence does not fully meet the criteria for the practically certain range (i.e., there is virtual certainty that the samples and the examined writings were not written by the same person).

Exception: This, like a definitive conclusion about identity, represents the highest degree of certainty when comparing handwritings. Using this degree of certainty, there is also no doubt that the writings in question and the comparison samples were not written by the same person. Often, this is the most challenging decision in document examination, especially in cases with a limited number of writings, such as single signatures.

Through understanding the handwriting process and proper preparation, it is possible to conduct competent forensic examinations and achieve accurate results.

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